

[4+2] Cycloaddition reaction : Synthesis and antifungal activities of 5-substituted-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidin-6-one derivatives

Babul C. Dutta^a, Susanta Kr. Borthakur^{a*}, Paran Boruah^b and Birendra N. Goswami^a

^aSynthetic Organic Chemistry Division, ^bMedicinal Aromatic & Economic Plant Division, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat-785 006, Assam, India

E-mail : skbthakur@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Syntheses and antifungal activities of 5-substituted-1,3-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidin-6-one from 2-benzylideneamino-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazole and ketenes formed *in situ* is described.

Keywords : Cycloaddition reaction, antifungal activities.

The thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidine ring system, received a lot of attention in the literature mainly due to its interesting biological properties associated with this ring system. The thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidine and its derivatives are reported to be insecticidal and accaricidal activity¹. These compounds are also reported to possess antimicrobial², anti-inflammatory^{3,4}, antitumor and immunomodulatory⁴ activities. In view of these observations, it has therefore, been considered of interest to synthesis some new thiazolo [3,2-*a*]pyrimidine derivatives. All these compounds have been synthesized from corresponding Schiff bases of 2-amino-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazoles by a [4+2] cycloaddition reaction with monophenyl ketene and diphenyl ketene formed *in situ* and the schematic presentation of the reaction sequence are given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

In our system a part of the heterocyclic moiety (4-phenyl-1,3-thiazole) incorporated with Schiff base comprises a heterodiene system and is the 4 π component in the Diels-Alder reaction. 5-Substituted-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidin-6-ones (**2**) were synthesized by

dropwise addition of phenylacetyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride or diphenylacetyl chloride in 1,4-dioxane to a solution of 2-benzylideneamino-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazole in 1,4-dioxane at 0–10 °C .

The structure of the compounds **2(a-l)** were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis and spectroscopic (IR, ¹H NMR and mass) data. The IR spectra of **2** showed $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at 1710 cm⁻¹ which is at much lower wave number than that for azetidinone carbonyl^{5,6}. The azetidinone molecule which is a strained four membered ring shows IR absorptions at high wavenumber (1775–1780 cm⁻¹). Suji⁷ studied the mass fragmentation modes of 1,3,4-thiadiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidinones to determine the position of CO in the 5-ones and isomeric 7-ones and observed intense ions corresponding to loss of CO from the molecular ion. In both these types of compounds a retro-Diels-Alder (RDA) process was observed. This type of intense ion peak attributed to the loss of CO and a RDA process were not observed in the pyrimidin-6-one compounds prepared here. These observations excluded the possible regioisomer 4-phenyl-1,3-thiazolo[3,2-*a*]pyrimidin-5-one derivatives (Tables 1 and 2).

Experimental

M.p.s were determined on a Buchi apparatus. Mass spectra were recorded with a Finnigan-MAT (INCOS 50) spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian T-60/90 MHz spectrometer. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazoles and its aryl Schiff bases were prepared following literature procedures⁸.

Note

Table 1. Physical data of compounds 2(a-l)

Compd.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. Formula (M ⁺)	Analysis (%) : Found (Reqd.)		
							C	H	N
2a	H	H	Ph	80	195	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO (382)	75.30 (75.39)	4.65 (4.71)	7.20 (7.33)
2b	4-OMe	H	Ph	82	192	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ SO ₂ (412)	72.60 (72.82)	3.79 (4.85)	6.51 (6.79)
2c	4-OMe	H	Cl	76	210	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₂ SClO (370)	61.50 (61.62)	3.98 (4.05)	7.50 (7.57)
2d	4-NO ₂	H	Ph	72	215	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ SO ₃ (427)	67.40 (67.45)	3.91 (3.98)	9.75 (9.84)
2e	4-Cl	H	Ph	72	210	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ SOCl (416)	69.00 (69.23)	4.13 (4.09)	6.70 (6.73)
2f	2-OH	H	Ph	78	190	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ SO ₂ (398)	72.50 (72.36)	4.45 (4.52)	7.00 (7.04)
2g	4-NMe ₂	H	Cl	73	185	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₃ SOCl (383)	62.50 (62.66)	4.72 (4.69)	10.80 (10.97)
2h	2-OH 4-OMe	H	Ph	78	180	C ₂₅ H ₂₀ N ₂ SO ₃ (428)	70.10 (70.09)	4.62 (4.67)	6.50 (6.54)
2i	H	H	C ₆ H ₄ N (CO) ₂	72	200	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ SO ₃ (451)	69.05 (69.18)	3.60 (3.77)	9.30 (9.31)
2j	H	Ph	Ph	70	185	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ SO (458)	78.45 (78.60)	4.76 (4.80)	6.09 (6.11)
2k	4-Cl	Ph	Ph	71	200	C ₃₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ SClO (492)	73.15 (73.17)	4.25 (4.27)	5.57 (5.69)
2l	4-NMe ₂	Ph	Ph	75	192	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ N ₃ SO (501)	76.55 (76.64)	5.28 (5.39)	8.35 (8.38)

Table 2. IR and ¹H NMR spectral data of the compounds 2(a-l)

Compd.	IR (KBr, v cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR
		(CDCl ₃ +DMSO-d ₆) δ, TMS = 0, ppm
2a	1710 (C=O), 1605 (C=N)	3.45 (1H, s), 3.50 (1H, s), 6.80–7.70 (16H, m, Ar-H)
2b	1710 (C=O), 1610 (C=N)	3.35 (3H, s), 3.80 (1H, s), 3.85 (1H, s), 6.80–7.90 (15H, m, Ar-H)
2c	1705 (C=O), 1610 (C=N)	3.35 (3H, s), 3.75 (1H, s), 3.85 (1H, s), 6.50–7.80 (10H, m, Ar-H)
2d	1712 (C=O), 1615 (C=N)	3.90 (1H, s), 3.95 (1H, s), 6.90–8.00 (15H, m, Ar-H)
2e	1710 (C=O), 1615 (C=N)	3.70 (1H, s), 3.75 (1H, s), 6.50–7.40 (15H, m, Ar-H)
2f	1710 (C=O), 1625 (C=N)	3.70 (1H, s), 3.76 (1H, s), 5.80 (1H, s), 7.00–7.80 (15H, m, Ar-H)
2g	1710 (C=O), 1625 (C=N)	2.15 (6H, s), 3.75 (1H, s), 3.80 (1H, s), 6.90–7.80 (10H, m, Ar-H)
2h	1710 (C=O), 1625 (C=N)	3.40 (3H, s), 3.75 (1H, s), 3.80 (1H, s), 5.50 (1H, s), 6.50–8.00 (14H, m, Ar-H)
2i	1710 (C=O), 1625 (C=N)	3.40 (1H, s), 3.47 (1H, s), 6.30–8.00 (15H, m, Ar-H)
2j	1718 (C=O), 1625 (C=N)	3.90 (1H, s), 6.60–7.40 (21H, m, Ar-H)
2k	1715 (C=O), 1610 (C=N)	3.85 (1H, s), 6.50–7.80 (20H, m, Ar-H)
2l	1720 (C=O), 1615 (C=N)	2.15 (6H, s), 3.92 (1H, s), 6.20–7.50 (19H, m, Ar-H)

Preparation of 4-phenyl-1,3-thiazol[3,2-a]5,5-diphenyl pyrimidin-6-one (3j) :

In a typical experiment, to a solution of 2-benzylideneamino-4-phenyl-1,3-thiazole (**1a**) (0.264 g, 0.001 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (20 ml) was added triethylamine (1 ml) and to this solution was added diphenylacetyl chloride (0.230 g, 0.001 mol) in dioxane dropwise at 0–10 °C with stirring for 30 min on a magnetic stirrer. The stirring was continued at 0–10 °C for 1 h more. The reaction mixture was brought to room temperature and kept stirring for another 4 h and then heated to 90–100 °C, while stirring continued. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into ice (100 g) and extracted with chloroform (2 × 40 ml), and dried over Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a pale yellow solid (**3j**), yield 0.33 g, m.p. 185 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm⁻¹) 1625 (C=N) and 1718 (C=O); ¹H NMR (δ ppm, CDCl₃ + DMSO-*d*₆) 3.90 (1H, s, C-1, benzylic proton), 6.60–7.40 (21H, m, Ar-H); mass *m/z* 458 (M⁺), 194 (Ph₂C=C=O).

Antifungal activity :

The thiazolo ring system is associated with broad spectrum biological activities. Therefore, we screened the thiazolo pyrimidine derivatives for their antifungal activities against *Rhizoctoniasolani* and *Drechslera oryzae*, two important fungal pathogens causing diseases on rice crop. Their antifungal activity was evaluated according to the inhibition zone technique⁹. The compounds **3a**, **3j** and **3l** were found more effective against *Rhizoctonia solani* at a concentration of 1 mg/ml and the compounds **3j** and **3g** were more effective against *Drechslera oryzae*,

at same concentration. The control (without treatment) sets of experiments with both the fungal pathogens exhibited no inhibition of growth. However, the standard fungicide (Carbendazim) showed 98.56 and 98.26% inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Drechslera oryzae* respectively at the same concentration of 1 mg/ml.

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